

Using a Transdisciplinary Lens to Make Sense of My Own Acquisition and Retrieval of Spoken English

Michael Burri¹

Wenzhou-Kean University, China, and University of Wollongong, Australia

ABSTRACT

Narratives and personal accounts of language learning experiences provide valuable insights into language development. However, the process by which multilinguals access and retrieve spoken language is not well understood. This paper aims to use a transdisciplinary perspective that draws on the interconnected areas of Mind (psychology), Brain (neuroscience), Health (well-being), and Education to explore my own English language acquisition and retrieval process. I acquired spoken English as a young child in the USA, lost the language while living in Switzerland for 18 years, and then rapidly retrieved it as a 22-year-old English language learner in New Zealand. Taking this transdisciplinary perspective and answering four key questions sheds light on my rather unusual 'spoken English journey.' The paper concludes with a discussion about pedagogical implications for language teachers.

Keywords: bilingualism; language acquisition; language retrieval; spoken English; transdisciplinary

¹ Correspondence: Michael Burri: mburri@kean.edu; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0115-5349>

INTRODUCTION

English is the most widely spoken language in the world, with roughly 1.5 billion speakers using it in one form or another (Patel et al., 2022). Because the development of English competence has been linked to economic gains and employment benefits, governments worldwide have made English a mandatory subject at primary school level and beyond (e.g., Garton & Copland, 2022; Zein & Butler, 2024). Yet, the exact age at which humans learn an additional language most effectively is an area that continues to be debated.

As a young child living in the USA, I spoke English fluently but was also able to communicate with my mom and dad in Swiss-German. I was a bilingual kid who used two languages regularly (Wodniecka et al., 2020). Right before I turned four, we moved to Switzerland, and as soon as we arrived, my spoken English began to deteriorate. Having to take mandatory English classes in middle school for three years made no difference. By the age of 22, I could no longer retrieve – or easily access – English, and thus was unable to converse in the language I had spoken fluently as a boy. Being in possession of American citizenship, I felt reasonably embarrassed and therefore decided to travel to New Zealand (NZ) with the goal of not only skiing the beautiful Southern Alps, but more importantly, regaining English proficiency. Upon commencing my studies, I was placed in the lowest level at a private language school in Christchurch. However, I soon began to excel and gained relatively high English fluency, with a near-native accent, within a few months.

Why was I able to learn – or more accurately, *retrieve* – spoken English within a few months and attain native-like proficiency in New Zealand at the age of 22? This is a legitimate question given that how bilinguals access and process language is still not well understood (Wodniecka et al., 2020), as well as the proposition that conversational proficiency in an additional language can take two or three years to develop (Cummins, 1999). I have presented at international conferences (e.g., Burri, 2023, July) and written about some of my language learning and professional experiences (Burri, 2022). However, as a teacher educator and researcher, I have always wanted to take a deep dive into neuroscience to help me understand the reasons for initially acquiring spoken English as a young child in the USA, forgetting it in Switzerland, and then retrieving the once forgotten language quite rapidly as an adult in NZ. The opportunity to explore this process arose during my sabbatical in 2024, as a student in the (online) *Neuroscience of Learning* course offered through the Harvard Extension School.

I should point out that the goal of my pursuit of finding answers and writing this paper was not a gratification of my successes as a second language (L2) learner, but rather a desire to contribute to the understanding of language learning and subsequently propose some implications for language teaching based on my own unique experiences.

The need for a transdisciplinary perspective on language acquisition

Narratives of L2 learning experiences (e.g., Hiver et al., 2019) and personal accounts, such as Casanave's (2012) documentation of her informal learning of Japanese, have provided valuable insights into L2 development. However, this L2 learning process differs for individuals who are brought up bilingual from birth, as their brains are slightly different from those of someone acquiring an additional language later in life (Li et al., 2024). Moreover, learning a language in the first few years, only to lose it and then eventually retrieve it, is an under-researched area that warrants further exploration.

Applied linguists have pointed out the importance of transdisciplinarity (e.g., Filipović, 2019; Perrin & Kramsch, 2019) with research combining bilingualism, L2 learning, neuroscience, and applied linguistics (e.g., Cohen, 1980; Fabbro, 1999; Morgan-Short & van Hell, 2023; Nouri, 2015; Suzuki et al., 2023; van Hell, 2023) to understand the process of acquiring one, two, or multiple languages. Yet, few seem to have taken a transdisciplinary perspective that draws on Mind (psychology), Brain (neuroscience), Health (well-being), and Education (MBHE; Tokuhama-Espinosa et al., 2023) to explore one's own language learning endeavours. As such, there is relatively little research on the process of acquiring a language as an adult. Using a transdisciplinary (i.e., MBHE) lens is, therefore, important because it allows me to explore this issue from different but intertwined perspectives and subsequently gather articles, evidence, and answers from multiple fields to help me make sense of my rather unusual 'spoken English journey.' This is, of course, a subjective undertaking based on my own experiences; therefore, if this paper were written by other bilinguals, it would likely look quite different. Nonetheless, I believe a self-study (rather than a typical empirical paper) in which the author takes a transdisciplinary perspective makes a valuable contribution because it may provide important and unique insights into language learning, and, more specifically, into how bilinguals access and process language.

Searching the literature for answers

My attempt to find answers in the *Neuroscience of Learning* course began with identifying key journal articles, book chapters, and books published in high-quality journals and authored by leading scholars within the last decade. Ten years was not necessarily a fixed timeframe, but it allowed me to narrow the search for publications dealing with bilingualism and language acquisition. I made extensive use of Google Scholar and relevant keywords in my search for readings. However, the search was also guided by weekly ‘bundles’ provided in the online platform of the *Neuroscience of Learning* course. A bundle is a Word document that lists dozens of MBHE resources (e.g., articles, links to YouTube clips) relevant to the weekly topic covered in the course. I first downloaded the bundle and then scanned the titles of all the provided resources. If a reading appeared to be relevant to my topic of investigation, I downloaded it and read the abstract and conclusion. Once done, I either discarded the paper or read it in its entirety, taking notes on key points applicable to my journey of acquiring and improving spoken English. This type of selective, yet in-depth reading of MBHE (i.e., transdisciplinary) literature gradually augmented my understanding of issues surrounding the acquisition and retrieval process of my spoken English. It should be noted, however, that the selected publications were not equally balanced among the four MBHE areas. The subjective nature of my literature search, time constraints, and/or specific use of keywords likely resulted in most publications drawing from Brain (neuroscience) and Education (applied linguistics/language), with fewer articles from Mind (psychology) and Health. While this imbalance was not ideal, the selected publications provided me with a new understanding of how I initially acquired English, lost it, and eventually retrieved it as an adult.

Accessibility of this paper and four key questions

While answers to my question of acquiring and retrieving spoken language were available in the literature, many of the journal articles I read were written in complex, scientific language. Therefore, this paper connects the literature with my own experiences of retrieving spoken English in an attempt to make neuroscience more accessible and meaningful to language teachers and researchers. At the same time, linking my story to MBHE Science may also help refute some specific myths – or false beliefs – about, for example, bilingualism or multilingualism commonly held around the world (Betts et al., 2019; Tan & Amiel, 2022; Tokuhama-Espinosa, 2018).

One broad question that has been on my mind and thus guides this paper is: *How and to what extent did exposure to spoken English in my early years influence the successful retrieval of spoken English after almost two decades of non-use?* Numerous influential, yet somewhat dated, theories offer answers, including Krashen's (1982) Second Language Acquisition Theory, which posits five hypotheses (acquisition-learning, monitor, input, affective filter, and natural order), Long's (1981) Interaction Hypothesis, and Sociocultural Theory (Lantolf & Thorne, 2006). In other words, there are dozens of possible reasons for my English retrieval in NZ. However, based on an initial review of the MBHE literature, I narrowed in on four key questions that I thought related exceptionally well to my own lived experiences, and, ultimately, helped me answer my broad question.

I will now present the four key questions and connect each one to current MBHE research and literature, signifying a transdisciplinary perspective to make sense of my process of acquiring and retrieving spoken English. The key questions include: (1) *Does the Relationship of Brain Plasticity with 'Use it or Lose it' Explain the Ability to Retrieve Spoken Language?*; (2) *Are People Born with an Innate Ability to Retrieve Spoken Language?*; (3) *Does a Child's Language Environment Impact the Retrieval of Spoken Language Later in Life?*; and (4) *Does the Impact of Emotions on Memory Facilitate the Retrieval of Spoken Language?* In each question, key concepts are first defined and discussed, followed by evidence and examples from my own life.

Key question 1: Does the relationship of brain plasticity with 'use it or lose it' explain the ability to retrieve spoken language?

Learning alters the structure of the brain, a phenomenon known as *plasticity* (Costandi, 2016). As the green part in Figure 1 shows, the small gaps at the end of a neuron (brain cell) are called *synapses*; that is, the place where neurons connect with each other through chemical and electrical signals. At these gaps, electric signals pass from one neuron to the next one and neurotransmitters (chemicals) are released. Through practice and repetition, the connections between the neurons are strengthened. Thus, as proposed by Hebb (1949) more than 70 years ago, 'neurons that fire together, wire together' is the physiological mechanism (plasticity) believed to result in learning.

Figure 1. Neurons connecting at synapses

Note: The image was taken from Creative Commons (i.e., open access).

Importantly, while the brain is remarkably plastic during the early years, it continues to change throughout life (Cozolino, 2013; Power & Schlaggar, 2017). That is, plasticity continues “throughout life, in response to everything we do and every experience we have” (Costandi, 2016, p. 2) and “it is likely that millions of synapses are modified in the human brain every second in one way or another” (p. 66). This synaptic modification creates and strengthens neural pathways in the brain, enabling us to improve at what we do, including language learning (Kail & Isel, 2021). As such, the brain adapts to what it does most, but learning something new at an older age is more difficult because we must override old and existing neural pathways with new ones.

Everything works within neural networks – “or basic brain circuitry” (Tokuhamas-Espinosa, 2019, p. 1) in the brain. Notably, research has shown that bilingualism shapes the brain’s structure (Pliatsikas et al., 2020; van Hell, 2023). Having access to and using two languages appears to increase grey matter density (the number of neurons) and white matter integrity (myelinated axons; see the following paragraph). Changes in brain structure can take place in a relatively short period of time and at all ages, but the process is sensitive to several factors, including similarity of the two languages, individual speaker differences, acquisition age, and gender (Li et al., 2014). However, as Schwieter and Rastelli (2023) point out, “[e]arly bilingualism – a linguistic situation in which an individual is exposed to more than one language from birth – changes a child’s brain organisation” (p. 366).

My own experiences with acquiring, forgetting, and retrieving spoken English support Schwieter and Rastelli's suggestion that "*some of these changes persist over the speaker's lifespan*" (p. 366, emphasis added). In combination with bilingual adults' strong ability to control their own behaviour and actions – i.e., their executive control (Bialystock, 2009) – plasticity appears to play an important role in language use and retrieval.

A closer examination of myelination, pruning, and remyelination offers further insights. As the grey parts in Figure 1 show, myelination is a fatty and multi-layered sheath that surrounds the axon of a neuron (Kaller et al., 2017; Tomassy et al., 2016). Myelination not only facilitates the electric signal to travel down the axon faster, thus strengthening the connection and communication between neurons, but it is also caused by repeated practice (rehearsal) of a particular skill or behaviour. Put differently, if the myelin sheath has been sufficiently developed, access and retrieval of stored information in the brain are achieved more quickly (Tokuhama-Espinosa, 2019). It is, therefore, reasonable to assume that being able to speak English fluently in the USA resulted in an increase in white matter (i.e., strong myelination) and long-term competence (Tu et al., 2015), which then allowed me to retrieve my spoken English in NZ.

Pruning occurs when the brain eliminates synapses, and myelin loss occurs because a skill or behaviour is not rehearsed enough or is no longer used (Xin & Chan, 2020). Pruning, therefore, leads to more efficient neural networks in the brain as less real estate is required to complete a task. This is a natural process, and the brain almost always overconnects before it refines its networks. Nevertheless, in terms of language control and use, if a speaker is removed from an enriched language environment and exposure to that language begins to decrease, such as my English in Switzerland, spontaneous production also decreases (Tu et al., 2015). From a plasticity point of view, because I ceased to speak English in Switzerland, the notion of 'use it or lose it' explains why I began to forget English. However, why did my spoken English return so quickly when I moved to New Zealand? Recent research suggests that the synaptic connections remained, but the axons were remyelinated (e.g., Bloom et al., 2022; Neely et al., 2022; Quan et al., 2022), whilst being motivated to learn and spending time in an English immersion environment in NZ. Living in Switzerland meant that I did not have easy access to the language. However, my adult English immersion in NZ reinforced past learning and most likely augmented the remyelination of axons, possibly allowing me to retrieve my spoken English rapidly.

Key question 2: Are people born with an innate ability to retrieve spoken language?

Over the last 100 years, a plethora of theories have been proposed for how first and additional languages are acquired (see Broad, 2020, for a brief overview). The theory most relevant to my second key question is Chomsky's (1965, 2015) hypothesis that all children are born with an innate set of grammatical principles common to all languages (see also Farid et al., 2021). Based on this premise, all humans possess an innate language sense; therefore, certain principles of language do not need to be learned, as they are hardwired into a child's brain and genes.

While Chomsky's proposition has been highly influential, his views have been criticised for ignoring the need to consider the triggers of language development, the social nature of language use, and the individual nature of language development (Cook, 2016). Nevertheless, contemporary neuroscientific understanding supports Chomsky's idea in that genes do "play a substantial role in shaping human behaviour" (Barlow, 2019, p. 74), and neural networks "are inherited through our genes and [then] strengthened through our daily experiences" (Tokuhama-Espinosa, 2019, p. 1). Clearly, genes appear to play a significant role in learning; however, the study of genes is a complex area, and their exact relationship to learning remains poorly understood (Thomas et al., 2015). Yet, because genes are heritable, it could mean that I was born with a specific genetic language makeup and abilities (Eising et al., 2022) that I inherited from my mom and dad. Multilingualism has been a part of my family for generations. My mom, for example, learned English in the USA, but was already fluent in three other languages: Swiss-German, German, and French. It could be that this particular epigenetic tag (Ortuño-Sahagún et al., 2019) – or from a Chomskyan perspective, genetic predisposition to have a gift for languages – enabled me to retrieve my spoken English quite rapidly as an adult in NZ. I may have also inherited a 'good language ear' and/or auditory memory. A heightened sensitivity to different sounds (e.g., the phonemes 'm', 'e', and 't' in *met*) and thus the ability to process auditory input may have not only facilitated my English language learning process (e.g., Saito et al., 2021, 2022) but it might have facilitated language retrieval in NZ.

However, one's genetic make-up does not necessarily determine how well someone acquires a language or accelerates at something. Only 10% of our genes get expressed – or turned on (Cantor, 2021) – because genes, environmental conditions, relationships, and experiences all interact together in shaping observable characteristics (e.g., eye colour, height) and in forming the foundation of brain architecture during the early years of a child (Fox et al, 2010). Thus, I now

turn to the third key question, which focuses on the language environments in the USA and Switzerland.

Key question 3: Does a child's language environment impact the retrieval of spoken language later in life?

The home and language environment in which a child grows up creates specific neural pathways and thus contributes to speech development (Bergelson et al., 2023). Yet, as Thomas and colleagues (2015) discuss, individual differences in motivation, achievement, and abilities result from the environment interacting with an individual's unique genetic profile; therefore, "the same genes may be [shaped] differently in different environments" (p. 75). Hence, this section discusses two specific periods in my early childhood life that may provide insights into the retrieval of my spoken English in NZ: (1) the English and Swiss-German environment in the USA, and (2) the Swiss-German environment in Switzerland.

English and Swiss-German environment in the USA

Evidence from neuroscience suggests that the sensitivity to different sounds of a language is established sometime between five months of gestation and three years of age. Kuhl and colleagues' (2006) research explored the perception of 6- to 12-month-old infants in the USA and Japan, showing that "exposure to a specific language causes neural commitment to the properties of native-language sounds" (p. F19). The researchers suggested that newborns are universal receivers of all language sounds and thus can hear any sounds of any language spoken in the world. However, the study also showed that this extraordinary ability begins to disappear around six months, as the brain starts to focus on the language of the environment in which the baby lives. In other words, the ability to perceive (or hear) sounds and then, ultimately, reproduce them in that particular language begins to be established after about six months of age. Although the notion of a critical period in language learning has been debated (see van Hell, 2023), Kuhl and colleagues' research demonstrated the existence of a specific time period in which both the age of the child and the environment play important roles in acquiring the sound system of a language. As such, learning two or more languages at a younger age when the brain is especially receptive and responsive to specific environmental experiences and exposures shapes bilingual brain architecture (Wei et al., 2015) and leads to changes in brain areas that are responsible for language control (see Tu et al., 2015, for a discussion of these areas).

It is, therefore, reasonable to suggest that being immersed in a social environment in which two languages (English and Swiss-German) were used regularly between my parents, brother, and I – and possibly even hearing the two languages all the time even if no one spoke directly to me in English (i.e., passive exposure; Kurkela et al., 2019) – contributed substantially to my bilingual development (Hoff & Core, 2015). That is, the neural pathways associated with auditory processing (Willmore & King, 2023) were well-rehearsed (i.e., myelinated), and due to substantial exposure to both languages, the neural networks of both my English and Swiss-German auditory systems were established during my four years in the USA. Also, with English and German belonging to the same Indo-European language family and, therefore, by being immersed in two historically similar languages with the same subject-verb-object structure (Tokuhama-Espinosa, 2008) and similar grammar, vocabulary, and sound patterns, my brain may have never pruned neural connections of either language in early childhood. Importantly, “[t]he earlier a second language is learned, the more similar [are] the neural language networks for the two languages” (Friederici, 2017, p. 155), and so memories of two historically similar languages, such as English and Swiss-German, were likely clustered together in neighbouring neural networks (Tokuhama-Espinosa, 2019). Thus, early exposure to both English and Swiss-German seems to have shaped my bilingual brain architecture, which contributed to the quick retrieval of my spoken English in NZ, even though I had not used the language for almost two decades.

Swiss-German environment in Switzerland

As discussed in the introduction, when I arrived in Switzerland, my spoken English began to deteriorate. Due to reduced exposure to English, the activation threshold in my bilingual mind likely began to increase, making access to and control of English more difficult (Tu et al., 2015; Wodniecka et al., 2020). At the same time, the need for group association and language socialisation (Duff & May, 2017) – using the local language to fit in, making Swiss-German-speaking friends, and becoming a member of the Swiss community for the following 18 years – made me favour Swiss-German over English, which, in turn, reduced lexical access and caused language attrition.

Casado and colleagues (2022) suggest that “[i]n speakers who know more than one language, all their languages remain active in their mind even when only one language is required in a given context” (n.p.). The bilingual brain, therefore, always has access to both languages, but it opts for the better choice when a word in two languages needs to be chosen (Sudarshan & Baum, 2019). This seems to be

a particular issue for bilinguals whose languages are not equally balanced because they not only require more effort to shuttle between languages than balanced bilinguals, but they need to work harder to inhibit the more dominant language in order to access and use words in the weaker language (Persici et al., 2019). As far as I remember, in the first few years of being in Switzerland, I was more proficient in English than in Swiss-German. Thus, my motivation to belong in school and, more broadly, the Swiss community might have inhibited my English for me to access, control, and use Swiss-German, resulting in eventually limited or even blocked lexical access in English.

At the same time, reduced exposure to English may have also caused language attrition, a gradual decline in English proficiency (see Schmid & Köpke, 2019). Chaouch-Orozco and Martín-Villena (2025) suggest that reduced exposure to a first language (L1) results in lexical attrition. That is, a bilingual may begin to experience difficulties with accessing and using their L1 words when immersed in an L2 environment. This might mean that being immersed in a Swiss-German environment impacted and restricted my English lexical memory network, thereby limiting my spoken English. My ability to organise and use Swiss-German vocabulary began to improve while my access to English words weakened. This, however, is speculative because numerous words (i.e., cognates) between Swiss-German and English overlap phonologically (e.g., *Bruder* vs *brother*), and also because of Oppenheim and colleagues' (2020) study showing that American children transitioning from Spanish-speaking homes to English-speaking primary schools did not necessarily experience Spanish attrition due to increased English use. A lot, of course, depends on the quantity and quality of language exposure, but in their research, the children's Spanish and English developed concurrently, with more notable increases in English proficiency.

In short, Swiss-German immersion may have made it challenging for me to access and use English in Switzerland. But, having been immersed in a bilingual English-Swiss-German environment in the USA as a young child, these early experiences might have allowed me to reactivate underused English language networks rather than having to create new neural pathways, resulting in relatively quick spoken English retrieval as an adult learner in NZ. Nevertheless, emotions and memory may have also played an important role, and therefore, the fourth key question explores whether the impact of emotions on memory facilitated the retrieval of my spoken English in NZ.

Key question 4: Does the impact of emotions on memory facilitate the retrieval of spoken language?

According to Betts and colleagues (2019), “[e]motions can affect human cognitive processes, including attention, learning and memory, reasoning, and problem-solving” (p. 8). In fact, there is no cognition without emotion (Immordino-Yang & Damasio, 2007). Therefore, emotions are always involved in memory formation, storage, and retrieval (Murray et al., 2013). That is, the physiology of the senses passes through our brain, following basically the same process: sensory perception (e.g., through smell or sight) – emotion – memory – learning. Figure 2 provides a simplified representation of the brain areas involved in emotions and cognitive processes, including the hippocampus, amygdala, and prefrontal cortex. In a nutshell, sensory input – for example, the smell of a fried chicken – travels up the brain stem to the (1) amygdala. The “emotional switch station” (Willis & Willis, 2020, p. 34), located near the centre of our brain, determines whether the smell is something to be fearful of. From there, it moves to (2) the prefrontal cortex, where decisions are made, and then, within a fraction of a second, the signal heads to (3) the hippocampus to confirm with long-term memory whether the smell is indeed fried chicken (Tyng et al., 2017).

Figure 2. Brain areas involved in emotions and cognitive processes

Note: The image was taken from Creative Commons (i.e., open access).

Emotions are not easily defined (Tyng et al., 2017), and a discussion between the differences of emotions and feelings is beyond the scope of this paper, but if memory is attached to an emotion, the (long-term) storage and retrieval of that memory is enhanced (Dolcos et al., 2020). Emotions are also part of our body, with recent research suggesting that they are controlled by different neurotransmitters (e.g., serotonin, dopamine, endorphins) in the brain (Wang et al., 2020). In other words, emotions are embodied. Embodiment theory suggests that emotions, thought, and language are intricately intertwined with motor processing (Damasio, 2021) – or, in other words, with movement – and thus influence a range of cognitive processes, including learning and meaning-making (Bergen, 2012).

Because language is embodied (Zappa et al., 2024), it plays a crucial role in the formation, storage, and retrieval of emotions and memories. That is, language helps us make sense of sensory input, perception, and experiences. By hearing the word "happiness," for example, language brings together sensory input, emotions, and memory, thus facilitating meaning-making (Lindquist et al., 2015). Both negative and positive emotions impact learning and memory formation (Shao et al., 2020).

Although emotions are embedded faster when they are negative (Salsano et al., 2024), positive emotions resulting from an emotionally safe, social, and linguistically rich English and Swiss-German home environment likely contributed to my bilingual brain development in the USA (Hartas, 2011; Wessels & Trainin, 2023). As discussed in the previous key question, this led to a strengthening in language pathways and as Costandi (2016) postulates, this “synaptic strengthening is indeed necessary and sufficient for memory formation” (p. 60). However, the notion of memory storage at the synaptic level has been questioned recently. Gersham (2023), for instance, argued that memory may be stored in molecules and is altered every time information is recalled, which could mean that language use influences memory formation. Irrespective of where and how memory is stored, being immersed in a safe social-emotional environment (Immordino-Yang et al., 2019) likely contributed to the formation of long-term memories associated with the English language, eventually facilitating the retrieval of spoken English in my early twenties in NZ.

In contrast, stress – a negative emotion – can be detrimental to learning (Shao et al., 2020). Ongoing (chronic) stress increases cortisol (i.e., a stress hormone), which, in turn, interferes with attention and negatively impacts memory. Put simply, stress impedes memory (Trammel & Clore, 2014) and thus learning. I

remember regularly experiencing stress, anxiety, and boredom during my time in middle school in Switzerland, and I did not enjoy the mandatory German, French, and English classes (see Pawlak et al., 2024, for an excellent volume on boredom in the language classroom). Moreover, my motivation to study English was extremely low because all my friends spoke Swiss-German, and with school success being largely measured in Swiss-German, I saw little purpose in studying foreign languages. Attention and memory are the cornerstone of learning (Tokuhama-Espinosa, 2019) and the combination of a lack of purposeful attention and low engagement most likely inhibited my spoken English, so I could use Swiss-German. This led me to ‘forget’ English until I decided to fly to NZ and enrol in an English language course in Christchurch.

SUMMARY

My four key questions have revealed that plasticity, as well as immersion in two historically similar languages and in an emotionally nurturing and linguistically rich environment, must have played important roles in English acquisition during my early years in the USA and in the eventual retrieval of the language in NZ. It is also possible that I had inherited a certain genetic language ability and/or auditory memory from my parents that then contributed to my ability to retrieve English in NZ. Furthermore, the third and fourth key questions showed that after moving to Switzerland, reduced exposure to English, a desire to make friends, ongoing stress, anxiety, boredom, and a lack of motivation and school engagement, most likely caused English language inhibition and a gradual proficiency decline, leading me to forget the language I once spoken fluently as a young boy in the USA.

Taking a transdisciplinary perspective and drawing on the interconnected areas of mind, brain, health, and education (i.e., MBHE Science) has provided several potential answers and explanations for the acquisition and retrieval of my spoken English. Before ending the paper, I will now briefly discuss two specific pedagogical implications: (1) the consideration of students’ emotional states, and (2) the integration of new information into students’ existing knowledge of language. These implications, like the other parts of this paper, are subjective and derived from my own unique experiences; nonetheless, I believe they hold pedagogical value and contribute to the discussion of enhancing students’ language learning process in the classroom.

Pedagogical implications

As discussed in the fourth key question, I was often stressed, anxious, and bored in middle school, with emotional triggers, such as stress, anxiety, and boredom in the classroom, impeding learning and impacting memory. Rodski (2019) argues that “[t]he basic cause of all stress is the perception that you can’t control a situation the way you want to” (p. 107) and when “confronted with relentless demands and unexpected challenges, we tend to slip into negative emotions” (p. 100) that impede learning. However, low to mild levels of stress – called ‘eustress’ (Kloidt & Barsalou, 2024) – activate the amygdala, prompt the hippocampus to consolidate memory, and stimulate alertness. It is, therefore, paramount for teachers to consider the emotional state of their students and maintain an appropriate level of challenge and stress. Thus, “[k]eeping students in a neuroplastic ‘sweet spot’ of arousal is a core element in the art of teaching” (Cozolino, 2013, pp. 81-82). If this is achieved, students will feel safe in the L2 classroom and be more likely to take risks and experiment with new language, thereby enhancing their language learning process in a secure and positive classroom environment.

In considering students’ emotional states, teachers should strive to create an enjoyable L2 classroom environment, irrespective of their students’ age and proficiency levels. This may include the occasional use of fun and engaging class activities that require little cognitive demand, such as watching a funny movie clip or having students share something about their own culture. L2 teachers should also actively promote the notion that it is never too late to learn an additional language because “our brain is plastic and capable of learning throughout the lifespan” (Nouri, 2015, p. 41). This reduces the pressure on students, especially when the value in the classroom is placed on the use of two or more languages, and if L2 learning is embraced as a complex and multifaceted process rather than a race toward the unrealistic goal of attaining native speaker proficiency in the target language (van Hell, 2023). Creating an emotionally safe, trusting, and enjoyable classroom atmosphere is paramount to enhance learning, but it is equally important for L2 teachers, given the emotionally stressful nature of language teaching (Gkonou et al., 2020).

Also relevant is that, even though I gradually forgot English in Switzerland, my neural pathways of the English language had been established in the USA. Prior knowledge of language (or any other knowledge) connects with and facilitates the integration of newly learned information into existing knowledge, which, in turn, improves the efficiency of learning (McDermott & Zerr, 2019). My experience

supports Chakraborty and Esposito's (2024) research, suggesting that connecting new language learning with previously learned or known language facilitates the reactivation – or retrieval – of this new language; in my case, English. In terms of classroom application, this means that language teachers would be well-advised to connect newly introduced language features to language their students have already studied or are familiar with (Lindsay & Gaskell, 2010). This could, for instance, entail a comparison of grammatical similarities between two languages, such as Swiss-German and English. Comparing language structures facilitates positive crosslinguistic transfer (van Hell, 2023) and thus augments learning. Or, teachers could introduce a new vowel sound and then link it to a previously learned sound or a specific one that students have in their first language, further illustrating the similarities between the two languages. Making such connections, ideally in combination with the consideration of learners' backgrounds and maintenance of an appropriate level of stress, most likely enhances the language learning process, especially between two languages that belong to the same language family, such as English and Swiss-German.

Finally, it is worth noting that the relationship between instructional methods and brain activity during language learning is not well understood (van Hell, 2023). Nonetheless, considering students' emotions and the connection between new content and existing knowledge are two practical ideas, although several other implications could, of course, be derived from a language journey such as the one described and analysed in this paper. I hope this paper prompts readers to consider some additional pedagogical suggestions.

Conclusion

Exploring the four key questions has shed some light on the acquisition and retrieval process of my spoken English. Yet, learning is a dynamic and personal process (Immordino-Yang & Gotlieb, 2018). The formation of neural pathways depends on the immediate environment in conjunction with previous experiences (Tokuhama-Espinosa, 2019), with individual differences, including language aptitude and age, playing key roles in the language learning process, memory formation, and storage of each individual learner (e.g., Li et al., 2014; Suzukida, 2021; Turker et al., 2021). As such, the selection and discussion of the four key questions and their pedagogical implications were a subjective undertaking based on my own lived experiences. The various aspects discussed in this article have not been tested empirically; in other words, their transferability to other learners in similar contexts is somewhat limited.

The relationship between the mind, culture, and language (e.g., Shaules, 2019) could also have been investigated to provide additional insight into my acquisition and retrieval process. This is an important area to examine, given Kitayama and colleagues' (2019) suggestion that culture influences our genetic structure. Writing this paper has, therefore, led me to ponder the composition of a follow-up article that focuses specifically on the impact of the immersion environment on my English language retrieval and competence in NZ. For now, I hope that taking a transdisciplinary perspective and engaging in a self-exploration of learning, forgetting, and eventually retrieving my spoken English has provided some new and meaningful insights into how bilinguals access and process language, thereby opening the floor for further discussion in this area.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

I would like to express my heartfelt gratitude to Professor Tracey Tokuhama-Espinosa and her teaching team. Their guidance and feedback were invaluable in shaping my thinking and helping me write this paper.

AUTHOR

Michael Burri is an Associate Professor in the Department of Curriculum and Instruction at Wenzhou-Kean University, and an Honorary Fellow in the School of Education at University of Wollongong. Prior to moving China, Michael taught/conducted research in Australia, Canada, and Japan. His professional interests include pronunciation instruction, teacher education/learning, Mind Brain Education, and the ethical use of GenAI. He has published in many leading journals, and his longitudinal research on learning to teach English pronunciation was awarded the TESOL Award for an Outstanding Paper on NNEST Issues (2015) and the MAK Halliday Prize for Outstanding Research in Applied Linguistics (2019).

REFERENCES

- Barlow, F. K. (2019). Nature vs. nurture is nonsense: On the necessity of an integrated genetic, social, developmental, and personality psychology. *Australian Journal of Psychology*, 71(1), 68–79.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/ajpy.12240>

- Betts, K., Miller, M., Tokuhama-Espinosa, T., Shewokis, P., Anderson, A., Borja, C., Galoyan, T., Delaney, B., Eigenauer, J., & Dekker, S. (2019). *International report: Neuromyths and evidence-based practices in higher education*. Online Learning Consortium.
- Bergelson, E., Soderstrom, M., Schwarz, I.-C., Rowland, C. F., Ramírez-Esparza, N., R. Hamrick, L., Marklund, E., Kalashnikova, M., Guez, A., Casillas, M., Benetti, L., Alphen, P. v., & Cristia, A. (2023). Everyday language input and production in 1,001 children from six continents. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, *120*(52), e2300671120.
<https://doi.org/doi:10.1073/pnas.2300671120>
- Bergen, B. K. (2012). *Louder than words: The new science of how the mind makes meaning*. Basic Books.
- Bialystok, E. (2009). Bilingualism: The good, the bad, and the indifferent. *Bilingualism: Language and Cognition*, *12*(1), 3–11.
<https://doi.org/10.1017/S1366728908003477>
- Bloom, M. S., Orthmann-Murphy, J., & Grinspan, J. B. (2022). Motor learning and physical exercise in adaptive myelination and remyelination. *ASN Neuro*, *14*.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/17590914221097510>
- Broad, D. (2020). Literature review of theories of second language acquisition. *Journal of Applied Linguistics and Language Research*, *7*(1), 80–86.
- Burri, M. (2022). From ESL student to teacher educator: Reflections on transnational and transcultural professional identity development. In G. Barkhuizen (Ed.), *Language teachers studying abroad: Identities, emotions and disruptions* (245–255). Multilingual Matters.
- Burri, M. (2023, July). *L2 teaching and learning: What does neuroscience have to do with this?*. Plenary given at the 4th Mekong TESOL Conference, Can Tho City, Vietnam.
- Cantor, P. (2021). All children thriving: A new purpose for education. *American Educator*, *45*(3), 14–26. Available at
<https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1322300.pdf>

- Casado, A., Szewczyk, J., Wolna, A., & Wodniecka, Z. (2022). The relative balance between languages predicts the degree of engagement of global language control. *Cognition*, 226, 105169.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cognition.2022.105169>
- Casanave, C. P. (2012). Diary of a dabbler: Ecological influences on an EFL teacher's efforts to study Japanese informally. *TESOL Quarterly*, 46(4), 642–670.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/tesq.47>
- Chakraborty, J., & Esposito, A. G. (2024). Adult learners self-derive new knowledge through integration of novel information and prior knowledge and are more successful with reactivation. *Mind, Brain, and Education*, 18(3), 226–235.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/mbe.12409>
- Chaouch-Orozco, A., & Martín-Villena, F. (2025). Network science reveals the early signs of L1 lexical attrition: Introducing the Lexical Attrition Foundation (LeAF) framework. *Bilingualism: Language and Cognition*, 28(1), 43–53.
<https://doi.org/10.1017/S1366728924000063>
- Chomsky, N. (1965). *Aspects of the theory of syntax*. The MIT Press.
- Chomsky, N. (2015). *Aspects of the theory of syntax: 50th anniversary edition*. The MIT Press.
- Cohen, A. D. (Ed.). (1980). *The neurolinguistics of second language learning*. Available at <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED202252.pdf>
- Cook, V. (2016). *Second language learning and language teaching* (5th ed.). Routledge.
- Costandi, M. (2016). *Neuroplasticity*. The MIT Press.
- Cozolino, L. (2013). *The social neuroscience of education: Optimizing attachment and learning in the classroom*. W. W. Norton & Company, Inc.
- Cummins, J. (1999). *BICS and CALP: Clarifying the distinction* (ERIC Document Reproduction Service No. ED438551).
- Damasio, A. (2021). *Feeling & knowing: Making minds conscious*. Robinson.

- Dolcos, F., Katsumi, Y., Moore, M., Berggren, N., de Gelder, B., Derakshan, N., Hamm, A. O., Koster, E. H. W., Ladoucer, C. D., Okon-Singer, H., Pegna, A. J., Richter, T., Schweizer, S., Van den Stock, J., Ventura-Bort, C., Weymar, M., & Dolcos, S. (2020). Neural correlates of emotion-attention interactions: From perception, learning, and memory to social cognition, individual differences, and training interventions. *Neuroscience & Biobehavioral Reviews*, *108*, 559–601. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neubiorev.2019.08.017>
- Duff, P. A., & May, S. (Eds.) (2017). *Language socialisation* (3rd ed.). Springer.
- Eising, E., Mirza-Schreiber, N., de Zeeuw, E. L., Wang, C. A., Truong, D. T., Allegrini, A. G., Shapland, C. Y., Zhu, G., Wigg, K. G., Gerritse, M. L., Molz, B., Alagöz, G., Gialluisi, A., Abbondanza, F., Rimfeld, K., van Donkelaar, M., Liao, Z., Jansen, P. R., Andlauer, T. F. M., . . . Fisher, S. E. (2022). Genome-wide analyses of individual differences in quantitatively assessed reading- and language-related skills in up to 34,000 people. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, *119*(35), e2202764119. <https://doi.org/doi:10.1073/pnas.2202764119>
- Fabbro, F. (1999). *The neurolinguistics of bilingualism: An introduction*. Psychology Press.
- Farid, A., Elbakai, F., & Fanani, A. (2021). Children's innate capacity of learning the first language: An overview of structure-dependent rules. *Journal of Research in Foreign Language Teaching*, *2*(1), 1–8.
- Filipović, J. (2019). Transdisciplinary qualitative paradigm in applied linguistics: Autoethnography, participatory action research and minority language teaching and learning. *International Journal of Qualitative Studies in Education*, *32*(5), 493-509. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09518398.2019.1597209>
- Fox, S. E., Levitt, P., & Nelson III, C. A. (2010). How the timing and quality of early experiences influence the development of brain architecture. *Child Development*, *81*(1), 28–40. <https://doi.org/10.1111%2Fj.1467-8624.2009.01380.x>
- Friederici, A. D. (2017). *Language in our brain: The origins of a uniquely human capacity*. The MIT Press.

- Garton, S., & Copland, F. (Eds.) (2022). *The Routledge handbook of teaching English to young learners*. Routledge.
- Gershman, S. J. (2023). The molecular memory code and synaptic plasticity: A synthesis. *Biosystems*, 224, 104825.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biosystems.2022.104825>
- Gkonou, C., Dewaele, J.-M., & King, J. (Eds.). (2020). *The emotional rollercoaster of language teaching*. Multilingual Matters.
- Hartas, D. (2011). Families' social backgrounds matter: Socio-economic factors, home learning and young children's language, literacy and social outcomes. *British Educational Research Journal*, 37(6), 893–914.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/01411926.2010.506945>
- Hebb, D. O. (1949). *The organization of behavior: A neuropsychological theory*. Wiley.
- Hiver, P., Obando, G., Sang, Y., Tahmouresi, S., Zhou, A., & Zhou, Y. (2019). Reframing the L2 learning experience as narrative reconstructions of classroom learning. *Studies in Second Language Learning and Teaching*, 9(1), 83–116. <https://doi.org/10.14746/ssllt.2019.9.1.5>
- Hoff, E., & Core, C. (2015). What clinicians need to know about bilingual development. *Seminars in Speech and Language*, 36(2), 89–99.
<https://doi.org/10.1055/s-0035-1549104>
- Immordino-Yang, M. H., & Gotlieb, R. J. M. (2018). An evolving understanding of social emotions from a mind, brain, and education perspective. In M. S. Schwartz & E. J. Paré-Blagoev (Eds.), *Research in mind, brain, and education* (pp. 73–96). Routledge.
- Immordino-Yang, M. H., & Damasio, A. (2007). We feel, therefore we learn: The relevance of effective and social neuroscience to education. *Mind, Brain, and Education*, 1(1), 3–10. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1751-228X.2007.00004.x>
- Immordino-Yang, M. H., Darling-Hammond, L., & Krone, C. R. (2019). Nurturing nature: How brain development is inherently social and emotional, and what

this means for education. *Educational Psychologist*, 54(3), 185–204.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/00461520.2019.1633924>

Kail, M., & Isel, F. (2021). Language, plasticity, and learning: Challenges at the forefront of research. *Language, Interaction and Acquisition*, 12(1), 1–9.
<https://doi.org/10.1075/lia.00012.int>

Kitayama, S., Varnum, M. E. W., & Salvador, C. E. (2019). Cultural neuroscience. In D. Cohen & S. Kitayama (Eds.), *Handbook of cultural psychology* (2nd ed.) (pp. 79–118). The Guilford Press.

Kloidt, J., & Barsalou, L. W. (2024). Establishing a Comprehensive Hierarchical construct of Eustress (CHE). *Current Psychology*, 43, 32258–32273.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s12144-024-06750-7>

Kuhl, P. K., Stevens, E., Hayashi, A., Deguchi, T., Kiritani, S., & Iverson, P. (2006). Infants show a facilitation effect for native language phonetic perception between 6 and 12 months. *Developmental Science*, 9(2), F13–F21.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-7687.2006.00468.x>

Kurkela, J. L. O., Hämäläinen, J. A., Leppänen, P. H. T., Shu, H., & Astikainen, P. (2019). Passive exposure to speech sounds modifies change detection brain responses in adults. *NeuroImage*, 188, 208–216.
<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2018.12.010>

Lantolf, J. P., & Thorne, S. L. (2006). *Sociocultural theory and the genesis of second language development*. Oxford University Press.

Li, P., Legault, J., & Litcofsky, K. A. (2014). Neuroplasticity as a function of second language

learning: Anatomical changes in the human brain. *Cortex*, 58, 301–324.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cortex.2014.05.001>

Li, J., Yao, C., Li, Y., Liu, X., Zhao, Z., Shang, Y., Yang, J., Yao, Z., Sheng, Y., & Hu, B. (2024). Effects of second language acquisition on brain functional networks at different developmental stages. *Brain Imaging and Behavior*, 18, 808–818.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11682-024-00865-y>

- Lindquist, K. A., MacCormack, J. K., & Shablack, H. (2015). The role of language in emotion: predictions from psychological constructionism. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 6, 444. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2015.00444>
- Lindsay, S., & Gaskell, M.G. (2010). A complementary systems account of word learning in L1 and L2: Learning words in L1 and L2. *Language Learning*, 60(s2), 45–63.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9922.2010.00600.x>
- Long, M. H. (1981). Input, interaction, and second language acquisition. *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences*, 379(1), 259–278.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1749-6632.1981.tb42014.x>
- Kaller, M. S., Lazari, A., Blanco-Duque, C., Sampaio-Baptista, C., & Johansen-Berg, H. (2017). Myelin plasticity and behaviour—connecting the dots. *Current Opinion in Neurobiology*, 47, 86–92.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conb.2017.09.014>
- Krashen, S. D. (1982). *Principles and practice in second language acquisition*. Pergamon Press.
- McDermott, K. B., & Zerr, C. L. (2019). Individual differences in learning efficiency. *Current Directions in Psychological Science*, 28(6), 607–613.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0963721419869005>
- Morgan-Short, K., & van Hell, J. G. (Eds.). (2023). *The Routledge handbook of second language acquisition and neurolinguistics*. Taylor & Francis.
- Murray, B. D., Holland, A. C., & Kensinger, E. A. (2013). Episodic memory and emotion. In M. D. Robinson, E. R. Watkins, & E. Harmon-Jones (Eds.), *Handbook of cognition and emotion* (pp. 156–175). The Guilford Press.
- Neely, S. A., Williamson, J. M., Klingseisen, A., Zoupi, L., Early, J. J., Williams, A., & Lyons, D. A. (2022). New oligodendrocytes exhibit more abundant and accurate myelin regeneration than those that survive demyelination. *Nature Neuroscience*, 25, 415–420. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41593-021-01009-x>

Nouri, A. (2015). Cognitive neuroscience of foreign language education: Myths and realities.

Iranian Journal of Research in English Language Teaching, 3(1), 40-47.

Oppenheim, G. M., Griffin, Z., Peña, E. D., & Bedore, L. M. (2020). Longitudinal evidence for simultaneous bilingual language development with shifting language dominance, and how to explain it. *Language Learning*, 70(S2), 20–44. <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1111/lang.12398>

Ortuño-Sahagún, D., Schliebs, R., & Pallàs, M. (2019). Editorial: Epigenetic mechanisms regulating neural plasticity. *Frontiers in Cellular Neuroscience*, 13, 118. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fncel.2019.00118>

Patel, M., Solly, M., & Copeland, S. (2022). *The future of English: Global perspectives*. British Council.

Pawlak, M., Kruk, M., & Zawodniak, J. (2024). *Teachers reflecting on boredom in the language classroom*. Equinox.

Perrin, D., & Kramsch, C. (Eds.) (2019). Transdisciplinarity in applied linguistics. *AILA Review*, 31(1). <https://doi.org/10.1075/aila.31>

Persici, V., Vihman, M., Burro, R., & Majorano, M. (2019). Lexical access and competition in bilingual children: The role of proficiency and the lexical similarity of the two languages. *Journal of Experimental Child Psychology*, 179, 103–125. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jecp.2018.10.002>

Pliatsikas, C., DeLuca, V., & Vois T., (2020). The many shades of bilingualism: Language experiences modulate adaptations in brain structure. *Language Learning*, 70(S2), 133–149. <https://doi.org/10.1111/lang.12386>

Power, J. D., & Schlaggar, B. L. (2017). Neural plasticity across the lifespan. *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews. Developmental Biology*, 6(1), 10.1002/wdev.216. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wdev.216>

Quan, L., Uyeda, A., & Muramatsu, R. (2022). Central nervous system regeneration: The roles of glial cells in the potential molecular mechanism underlying remyelination. *Inflammation and Regeneration*, 42(7), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41232-022-00193-y>

- Saito, K., Sun, H., Kachlicka, M., Robert, J., Nakata, N., & Tierney, A. (2022). Domain-general auditory processing explains multiple dimensions of L2 acquisition in adulthood. *Studies in Second Language Acquisition*, 44(1), 57–86.
<https://doi.org/10.1017/S0272263120000467>
- Saito, K., Suzukida, Y., Tran, M., & Tierney, A. (2021). Domain-general auditory processing partially explains L2 speech learning in classroom settings: A review and generalization study. *Language Learning*, 71(3), 669–715.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/lang.12447>
- Salsano, I., Tain, R., Giuliotti, G., Williams, D. P., Ottaviani, C., Antonucci, G., Thayer, J. F., & Santangelo, V. (2024). Negative emotions enhance memory-guided attention in a visual search task by increasing frontoparietal, insular, and parahippocampal cortical activity. *Cortex*, 173, 16–33.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cortex.2023.12.014>
- Schmid, M. S., & Köpke, B. (Eds.). (2019). *The Oxford handbook of language attrition*. Oxford University Press.
- Schwieter, J. W., & Rastelli, S. (2024). Neurolinguistics in language learning and teaching. In L. Wei, Z. Hua, & J. Simpson (Eds.) *The Routledge handbook of applied linguistics* (pp. 362–373). Routledge.
- Shao, K., Nicholson, L. J., Kutuk, G., & Lei, F. (2020). Emotions and instructed language learning: Proposing a second language emotions and positive psychology model. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 11, 2142.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.02142>
- Shaules, J. (2019). *Language, culture, and the embodied mind: A developmental model of linguaculture learning*. Springer
- Sudarshan, A., & Baum, S. R. (2019). Bilingual lexical access: A dynamic operation modulated by word-status and individual differences in inhibitory control. *Bilingualism: Language and Cognition*, 22(3), 537–554.
<https://doi.org/10.1017/S1366728918000111>
- Suzuki, Y., Jeong, H., Cui, H., Okamoto, K., Kawashima, R., & Sugiura, M. (2023). An fMRI validation study of the word-monitoring task as a measure of implicit knowledge: Exploring the role of explicit and implicit aptitudes in behavioral

- and neural processing. *Studies in Second Language Acquisition*, 45(1), 109–136. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0272263122000043>
- Suzukida, Y. (2021). The contribution of individual differences to L2 pronunciation learning: Insights from research and pedagogical implications. *RELC Journal*, 52(1), 48-61. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0033688220987655>
- Thomas, M. S. C., Kovas, Y., Meaburn, E., & Tolmie, A. (2015). What can the study of genetics offer to educators? *Mind, Brain and Education*, 9(2), 72–80. <https://doi.org/10.1111/mbe.12077>
- Tokuhama-Espinosa, T. (2008). *Living languages: Multilingualism across the lifespan*. Praeger Publishers.
- Tokuhama-Espinosa, T. (2018). *Neuromyths: Debunking false ideas about the brain*. W. W. Norton & Company Ltd.
- Tokuhama-Espinosa, T. (2019). *Five pillars of the mind: Redesigning education to suit the brain*. W. W. Norton & Company.
- Tokuhama-Espinosa, T., Simmers, K., Batchelor, D., Nelson, A. D., & Borja, C. (2023). A theory of mental frameworks. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 14(1220664). <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2023.1220664>
- Tomassy, G. S., Dershowitz, L. B., & Arlotta, P. (2016). Diversity matters: A revised guide to myelination. *Trends in Cell Biology*, 26(2), 135–147. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tcb.2015.09.002>
- Trammell, J. P., & Clore, G. L. (2014). Does stress enhance or impair memory consolidation? *Cognition & Emotion*, 28(2), 361–374. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1080%2F02699931.2013.822346>
- Tu, L., Wang, J., Abutalebi, J., Jiang, B., Pan, X., Li, M., Gao, W., Yang, Y., Liang, B., Lu, Z., & Huang, R. (2015). Language exposure induced neuroplasticity in the bilingual brain: A follow-up fMRI study. *Cortex*, 64, 8-19. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cortex.2014.09.019>
- Turker, S., Seither-Preisler, A., & Reiterer, S. M. (2021). Examining individual differences in language learning: A neurocognitive model of language

- apptitude. *Neurobiology of Language*, 2(3), 389–415.
<https://doi.org/10.1162/nol.a.00042>
- Tyng, C. M., Amin, H. U., Saad, M. N., & Malik, A. S. (2017). The influences of emotion on learning and memory. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 8, 1454.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2017.01454>
- Wang, F., Yang, J., Pan, F., Ho, R. C., & Huang, J. H. (2020). *Editorial: Neurotransmitters and emotions*. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 11(21), 1–3.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.00021>
- Wei, M., Joshi, A. A., Zhang, M., Mei, L., Manis, F. R., He, Q., Beattie, R. L., Xue, G., Shattuck, D. W., Leahy, R. M., Xue, F., Houston, S. M., Chen, C., Dong, Q., & Lu, Z. L. (2015). How age of acquisition influences brain architecture in bilinguals. *Journal of Neurolinguistics*, 36, 35–55.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jneuroling.2015.05.001>
- Wessels, S., & Trainin, G. (2023). From bilingual to biliteracy: Learning from families. *Early Childhood Education Journal*, 53, 315–326.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10643-023-01519-2>
- Willis, J., & Willis, M. (2020). *Research-based strategies to ignite learning: Insights from neuroscience and the classroom* (2nd ed.). ASCD.
- Willmore, B. D., & King, A. J. (2023). Adaptation in auditory processing. *Physiological Reviews*, 103(2), 1025–1058.
<https://doi.org/10.1152/physrev.00011.2022>
- Wodniecka, Z., Casado, A., Kałamała, P., Marecka, M., Timmer, K., & Wolna, A. (2022). The dynamics of language experience and how it affects language and cognition. In K. D. Federmeier & H-W. Huang (Eds.), *The psychology of learning and motivation, volume 72: Adult and second language learning* (pp. 235-281). Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/bs.plm.2020.02.005>
- van Hell, J. G. (2023). The Neurocognitive underpinnings of second language processing: Knowledge gains from the past and future outlook. *Language Learning*, 73(S2), 95–138 <https://doi.org/10.1111/lang.12601>
- Zappa, A., Bolger, D., Pergandi, J-M., Fargier, R., Mestre, D., & Frenck-Mestre, C. (2024). The neural correlates of embodied L2 learning: Does embodied L2

verb learning affect representation and retention?. *Neurobiology of Language*, 5(2), 360–384. https://doi.org/10.1162/nol_a_00132

Zein, S., & Butler, Y. G. (Eds.) (2024). *English for young learners in Asia: Challenges and directions for teacher education*. Routledge.